

School of Social Sciences & Professions AI Guidance:

How Educators Can Implement the Dual- Model Approach

Version 1.1, 2025

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Foreword

This guidance document was developed over a half-year period and has benefited from the input of SSSP colleagues. In particular, the SSSP AI Working Group provided invaluable advice; special thanks are extended to the members of this group: Adi Chereni, Alex Black, Brian Tutt, Claire Bradshaw, Edith Boadkye-Smith, Elsa Gonzalez Simon, Ieva Steinberga, Julius Elster, Mabel Encinas, Michael Harpham, Robin West, Steven Curtis, Yanbo Hu, and Wendy Ross. Michael Harpham also provided highly valued editorial feedback, helping to refine the final version of this document. Elements of critical insight and wisdom within this document should be attributed to these individuals.

The main argument of this document is that SSSP educators *must* update their practice because the recent arrival of AI tools (such as ChatGPT) has undermined the effectiveness of traditional teaching and learning (T&L) methods. This document offers readers two models to guide their practice modifications: the Critical-Learning model and the Enhanced-Learning model. As a priority, educators should design-out the possibility that students will use AI tools to circumvent the traditional learning process - this is the Critical-Learning model. As a secondary, supplementary option, educators can focus on developing students' subject-relevant technological proficiency and AI literacy by allowing students to use AI tools - this is the Enhanced-Learning model. This guidance strongly recommends that each classroom activity or assessment should fully comply with only one model at a time. In application, this means educators have the option to integrate AI into their T&L practice but this should be a distinct addition to an otherwise AI-free process. This dual-model approach favours the Critical-Learning model because it posits that social science graduates with highly developed critical thinking skills and low levels of technological proficiency have a greater potential to positively shape society than those with the inverse.

Before concluding this foreword, it may be useful for readers to know more about my positionality as to better inform their own critical reading of the forthcoming guidance. I am a white British man; this is consequential in this context because of the distinct and problematic white masculine culture that reportedly surrounds the development of AI tools.¹ Thinkers such as Bender and Hanna² report that there is a dominating culture online and in the industrial sector which fixates on the potential benefits of AI tools while marginalising their negative consequences for people of colour, women and the planet. Rephrased, the dominant culture that surrounds AI tools is one that is most likely to favour myself, I am least likely to feel its negative effects: being white, I am the least likely to be a victim of racism; as a man, I am not the subject of misogyny; being a national and resident of a highly developed country, I am least likely

¹ Emily Bender and Alex Hanna, *The AI Con: How to Fight Big Tech's Hype and Create the Future We Want* (Harper 2025); Laura Bates, *The New Age of Sexism: How the AI Revolution Is Reinventing Misogyny* (Simon & Schuster 2025).

² Bates (n 1); Denise Turley, 'Breaking the Bro Culture: Why We Need More Women' (*Artificial Intelligence Accelerator Institute*, 3 September 2024) <[1](https://www.aiacceleratorinstitute.com/breaking-the-bro-culture-why-we-need-more-women-in-tech-and-ai/#:~:text=AI%20systems%20are%20trained%20on,algorithms%20that%20discriminate%20against%20women.> accessed 10 September 2025; Bender and Hanna (n 1).</p></div><div data-bbox=)

to feel the most severe impacts of climate change. I have reflected upon this positionality when authoring this document. To the best of my ability, I have sensitised myself to the concerns of people of colour, women and the impact AI tools have on the planet. In doing so, I have endeavoured to mitigate the risk that the guidance offered here is uncritical or neglects matters that obstruct the promotion of social justice.

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1. Introduction

1.1 The Purpose of This Guidance Document

The purpose of this document is to offer practical guidance to educators in the School of Social Sciences and Professions (SSSP) regarding how to understand and where appropriate, integrate artificial intelligence (AI) tools into their teaching and learning practice.

AI tools such as that of OpenAI's ChatGPT and Google's Gemini have significantly increased in popularity since 2022, this has changed students' and educators' behaviour in the T&L process. A recent Higher Education Policy Institute (HEPI) survey of approximately 1,000 undergraduates found that, "almost all students (92%) [are] now using AI in some form".³ Emerging research also demonstrates that academics regularly use AI tools. Indeed, a Jisc survey found that nearly 24% of educators used AI tools as part of their teaching practice;⁴ meanwhile, an Oxford University Press survey found that 76% of researchers used "some form of AI tool in their research".⁵ Evidentially, AI tools are no longer a niche technology outside of HE processes; they are now integrated into the daily practice of both students and staff.

Educators, university leaders and technologists have mixed thoughts about the disruptive impact of AI tools on the HE sector.⁶ On the one hand, some have raised concerns regarding how students are using AI tools to commit undetectable forms of plagiarism, and that such AI tools are eroding the development of students' critical thinking skills.⁷ Critics have also argued that AI is serving to deskill graduates to the point that it damages their employability; as one outlet reported, some graduates since 2022 are increasingly unable to perform expected tasks such as "speak on the phone or in meetings, take notes with a pen, relay messages precisely or complete written tasks without internet access".⁸ Adding to this criticism, others have argued that when educators use AI tools to support their teaching, they effectively become poor role models,

³ Josh Freeman, 'Student Generative AI Survey 2025' (Higher Education Policy Institute 2025) <<https://www.hepi.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/HEPI-Kortext-Student-Generative-AI-Survey-2025.pdf>>, 1.

⁴ Jisc, 'Teaching Staff Digital Experience Insights Survey 2023/24' <<https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/9702/1/DEI-2024-teaching-staff-he-report.pdf>> accessed 18 August 2025.

⁵ Oxford University Press, 'Researchers and AI Survey Findings' <<https://fdslive.oup.com/www.oup.com/academic/pdf/Researchers-and-AI-survey-findings.pdf>> accessed 15 August 2025, 4.

⁶ Eliza Compton, 'AI and Assessment in Higher Education' *Times Higher Education* (8 April 2025) <<https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/ai-and-assessment-higher-education>> accessed 7 August 2025; James Hutson and others, 'Artificial Intelligence and the Disruption of Higher Education: Strategies for Integrations across Disciplines' (2022) 13 *Creative Education* 3953.

⁷ Daniel L Mpolomoka and others, 'Artificial Intelligence-Related Plagiarism In Education: A Systematic Review' (2025) 12 *European Journal of Education Studies* <<https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/6029>> accessed 7 August 2025.

⁸ Jedidajah Otte, "'I've £90k in Student Debt – for What?' Graduates Share Their Job-Hunting Woes amid the AI Fallout' *The Guardian* (UK, 13 July 2025). <<https://www.theguardian.com/money/2025/jul/13/student-debt-graduates-share-job-hunting-woes-ai-fallout>> accessed 15 August 2025.

damage their institution's reputation and ultimately, such educators undermine the purpose of higher education.⁹

Meanwhile, AI advocates have emphasised that AI tools have enabled greater student accessibility and equity in the learning process as well as improved student completion rates.¹⁰ Others have gone further to argue that the integration of AI tools as a 'thought partner' into the T&L process has enhanced the development of students' critical thinking skills.¹¹ AI supporters have also argued that the HE sector should integrate such tools throughout students' educational journey because employers will expect graduates to be AI literate, to leverage this technology to efficiently complete the work of tomorrow's world.¹² In this sense, the integration of AI tools into the T&L process is necessary to boost students' employability. These opposing perspectives are the result of the rapidly emergent nature of contemporary AI tools; these tools are a surprise arrival technology, there is little empirical research on the impact of such tools on students. This guidance document was developed in this context. In recognition of the potential risks and benefits that AI tools can have in the T&L process, this document offers a 'how to' guide for SSSP staff, to help them navigate this evolving issue.

1.2 About This Guidance

This guidance has been created for educators who are module leaders and who teach students at the undergraduate level. This guidance is advisory only; none of the directions within this document are compulsory practice within SSSP. At present, there are no university-wide instructions regarding how course leaders should manage AI. As a separate project, additional course-level and institutional-level directions are likely to be developed in the near future, which include the formation of an AI policy or amendments to current policy as to integrate issues relating to AI. Any future policy instructions should be viewed as superseding the guidance offered here.

Readers should be aware that there are other guidance documents and courses provided by London Metropolitan University (LMU) to help both staff and students (see Section 1.7). Students, for example, have their own guidance that has usefully been compiled by LMU's library staff. There are also a number of pre-recorded lectures available from LMU's Centre for Teaching Enhancement (CTE) which provide advice to staff regarding how to set up an account with an AI tool and how such tools can be used in classroom activities.

The present guidance document does not address issues of disability and accessibility; the author understands that a specialist guidance document is currently being developed by LMU's Disability and Dyslexia Services (DDS) to address this. As much as possible, the guidance offered in this document aims to be bespoke to SSSP staff, to not repeat any of the guidance already

⁹ Kashmir Hill, 'The Professors Are Using ChatGPT, and Some Students Aren't Happy About It' *New York Times* (New York, 14 May 2025) <<https://www.nytimes.com/2025/05/14/technology/chatgpt-college-professors.html>> accessed 15 August 2025.

¹⁰ Hutson and others (n 6).

¹¹ Jennifer A Despain, 'Bridling, Taming and Riding the AI Beast', *10th International Conference on Higher Education Advances (HEAd'24)* (Universitat Politècnica de València 2024) <<http://ocs.editorial.upv.es/index.php/HEAD/HEAD24/paper/view/17378>> accessed 15 August 2025.

¹² Peter Waring, 'Artificial Intelligence and Graduate Employability: What Should We Teach Generation AI?' (2024) 7 *Journal of Applied Learning & Teaching* 22.

offered at a general level by the CTE or elsewhere. To this end, if readers feel that an issue they have has not been answered in this document, it is likely that it has been answered in one of the other supporting T&L resources listed in Section 1.7.

1.3 Main Argument of This Guidance

As referred to in the Foreword, the central argument of this document is that educators *must* update their practice in view of the recent emergence of AI tools. Traditional T&L practices can be undermined by such tools and a lack of action here poses a risk to the School's reputation. This document recommends that educators update their practice by embracing a dual-model approach. Namely, educators should follow the Critical-Learning model for the majority of their practice and if they see fit, to draw upon the Enhanced-Learning model in a supportive capacity, (Section 1.4 discusses these models in greater detail).

The reworking of assessments is particularly important; a lack of action here by educators places the university at significant reputational risk. AI tools enable users to generate vast amounts of textual analysis without needing to possess any significant critical thinking or research skills. The result is that AI tools are able to render unmodified, traditional forms of assessment such as essay writing obsolete. If educators use assessment methods that inaccurately evaluate students' skills and knowledge, the reputation of the university as a degree-awarding body will be significantly undermined.

1.4 The Dual-Model Approach

In view of the disruption caused by AI tools, this guidance document recommends that educators embrace a dual-model approach to T&L. In greater detail, educators should keep in mind two distinct models of teaching practice: the Critical-Learning model and the Enhanced-Learning model. The present guidance argues that while SSSP educators can employ both models, core T&L practice *must* follow the Critical-Learning model. Meanwhile, educators should view the Enhanced-Learning model as a guide for other optional, AI-inclusive forms of T&L practice. In using this dual-model approach, it is acceptable for educators to fully embrace the Critical-Learning practices and neglect Enhanced-Learning practices absolutely but it is not acceptable to do the reverse.

An analogy to help educators understand the dual-model approach is that of a ship with two sails. As module leaders begin the academic year, they are like a captain leading their passengers (students) on a set route. The mainsail that is absolutely required for the ship to make its journey is the Critical-Learning model. As an option, the captain (or module leader) could use a secondary, smaller sail (the Enhanced-Learning model) but this is not required to make the journey. The following subsections detail these models further and offer a justification for this dualist approach that favours the Critical-Learning model.

1.4.1 The Critical-Learning Model

The Critical-Learning model prioritises educators' capacity to develop their students' autonomous ability to critically think and reflect; as well as, educators' capacity to develop students' subject-relevant, non-digital, effective communication and problem-solving skills.¹³ In more practical terms, the Critical-Learning model requires educators to, as much as possible, *design-out students' ability to rely on AI tools when they engage with classroom activities and assessments*. In doing so, the Critical-Learning model encourages educators to create conditions that prevent traditional pedagogical practices from being ineffective due to the circumventing nature of AI tools. As a result of implementing this model, educators preserve the development and accurate assessment of students' critical thinking skills. For example, the Critical-Learning model advocates converting a traditional take-home essay into an exam-based, pen-and-paper essay. In this way, this model is wholly socially-oriented rather than technologically-oriented.

1.4.2 The Enhanced-Learning Model

As a secondary and optional form of T&L practice, educators can make use of the Enhanced-Learning model. In employing this model, educators focus on developing students' subject-relevant technological proficiency and AI literacy by allowing them to use AI tools in classroom activities and by offering AI-integrated assessments. For example, a classroom activity may require students to use AI tools to generate a mock email for a client which becomes the subject of critical, in-class discussion. Alternatively, in applying the Enhanced-Learning model, educators could revise traditional essays and dissertation projects so that they accept that students will use AI tools to assist them in completing these tasks. Importantly, educators should continue to uphold standard academic misconduct rules. In the case of an essay or dissertation project that accepts students' use of AI, plagiarism and falsified references are still recognised as academic misconduct. Students' otherwise uncritical applications of AI tools in completing such a project are simply marked down; reasons for marking down may include thin critical analysis, poor expression of ideas or inappropriate application of key theory. To reiterate, under the Enhanced-Learning model, students' use of AI tools alone is not grounds for failure. Indeed, when applying the Enhanced-Learning model, educators *accept* and *expect* students to use AI tools in a complementary manner to their standard critically reflective approach to completing a class activity or assessment. Appendix 5 offers further guidance on what is considered appropriate and inappropriate uses of AI for students.

1.4.3 Justification for the Dual-Model Approach (Which Favours the Critical-Learning Model)

While T&L practice may be entirely committed to the Critical-Learning model, the present guidance strongly advises against T&L practices being wholly committed to the Enhanced-Learning model. The present guidance recognises that technological skills (which includes being familiar with AI tools) are useful for a range of social science-related tasks. More valuable, however, is a social scientist's ability to navigate, understand, and resolve complex social issues - this does not necessitate technological ability. Indeed, while a person could use an AI tool to

¹³ These reflect LMU's prior value commitments detailed in the Education for Social Justice Framework (ESJF).

rapidly develop a research proposal or analyse data, what is more valuable is a person who can identify and resolve the errors in such a proposal and analysis. Rephrased, the present guidance takes the view that a critically trained social scientist unable to use AI tools is more valuable to academia and society than an advanced AI tool in the hands of an uncritical user. It is therefore acceptable for educators to redesign modules so that they are entirely reflective of the Critical-Learning model (and exclude any element of the Enhanced-Learning model). To reiterate, technological proficiency is not fundamental to social science-related work.

This dual-model approach also empowers educators and students to elect to not use AI tools if they choose. There are compelling ethical reasons for educators and students to refrain from using AI tools: the impact of these tools on the planet is significant, such tools have been criticised as being racist as well as misogynistic and the politics of AI leaders / CEOs is questionable. Such tools can produce racist outputs owing to how they are trained on colonised academic texts and publicly available social media posts. The dual-model approach aims to empower educators to control their level of engagement with AI tools. At the same time, educators should also afford this same choice to students; this means that for every Enhanced-Learning T&L activity or assessment, educators should allow for alternative Critical-Learning arrangements. In embracing this dualist approach, therefore, educators are able to preserve the value that social science-related degrees offer students while also upholding robust, inclusive, ethical standards.

1.5 Terms & Definitions

What follows is the present document's definition of 'AI tools' as well as what makes such tools 'generative', 'agentic' and '(near) general'. The term 'AI tools' is used as a catch-all when describing applications such as OpenAI's ChatGPT, Google's Gemini, Microsoft's CoPilot, xAI's Grok and High-Flyer's DeepSeek – which are the most popular AI models at present.¹⁴ In their simplest description, all of these tools operate as advanced chat bots that require users to provide an initial prompt or search query. A prominent problem when discussing AI is that there is no widely agreed definition of what sufficiently makes an AI tool generative, agentic or (near) general,¹⁵ while some have attempted to create sub-typologies to help thinkers parse these differences.¹⁶ For this reason, it is necessary to ground this document's terms here.

Generative AI tools are those that create responses based on a machine's prior training on vast amounts of pre-existing media/data. For example, a model such as ChatGPT could use its vast amounts of data on cats to generate a text-based description, image and/or video of a cat. The 'generative' aspect centres on synthesising prior data together to answer a user's query / prompt such as, "what does a cat look like?" In this sense, the outputs of such machines are the

¹⁴ LMArena (*Leaderboard Overview*, 7 August 2025) <<https://lmarena.ai/leaderboard>> accessed 7 August 2025.

¹⁵ Raphael Ronge, Markus Maier and Benjamin Rathgeber, 'Towards a Definition of Generative Artificial Intelligence' (2025) 38 *Philosophy & Technology* 31; Dena Kadhim Muhsen and Ahmed T Sadiq, 'Understanding Artificial General Intelligence: Characteristics and Benchmarks' (2025) 1 *Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Control Systems* 16.

¹⁶ Ronge, Maier and Rathgeber (n 16).

sophisticated reworking of prior human work. Whether this counts as producing something truly original is a matter that has attracted continuing legal debate in the US, UK and Europe.¹⁷

Agentic AI tools are those which are able to utilise many different programs (such as email, internet browsers and word processors) in order to answer a user’s prompt. Agentic AI is useful in that it can perform more long-chain, multi-step, decision-making tasks than what generative AI can achieve. For example, in response to the prompt “write a literature review on UK criminal justice policy over the past 30 years”, an advanced agentic AI tool could formulate and complete the following tasks: (1) search the internet for relevant literature, (2) access and download journals using the user’s account details (user name and password) forming a data base of relevant literature, (3) thematically code the collected data/literature using NVivo, (4) convert this NVivo analysis into a written thematic literature review using Microsoft Word. At the time of writing, agentic AI tools are the focus of the sector.

General AI is the proverbial holy grail of AI research, it is a form of AI which will be better at all technical tasks than all humans across disciplines and domains. It is difficult to conceptualise what such technology would look like in practice. This technology does not presently exist.

To help readers further, a glossary can be found at the back of this document. This section explains many of the frequently used terms that are used when discussing AI tools.

1.6 Structure of This Document

This document offers three main sections (or chapters), each detailing how AI tools can be used by educators in their practice. Section 2 focuses on how educators can, in a very limited capacity, use AI tools to support in the creation of T&L materials. Following this, Section 3 details how to update assessments using the dual-model approach. Lastly, Section 4 provides guidance on how educators can use AI tools to help resolve low-stakes administrative tasks.

Each of these sections presents suggested good practice (the “Dos”) alongside those practices to be avoided (the “Do Nots”). To reiterate Section 1.2 however, this is advisory guidance only – these instructions are not compulsory. At the end of Sections 2 and 3, a fictional example of good practice is offered to illustrate how this guidance can be applied. This document concludes with a comprehensive glossary of relevant AI and T&L terminology, and an appendix that offers a range of supporting documents that can be used by educators when updating their module handbooks and Weblearn pages, as well as an FAQ.

¹⁷ Intellectual Property Office, ‘Copyright and AI: Consultation’ (<https://www.gov.uk/>, December 2024) <<https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations/copyright-and-artificial-intelligence/copyright-and-artificial-intelligence#ministerial-foreword>> accessed 7 August 2025; Jason Bailey, ‘Disney and Comcast’s AI Lawsuit May Open a Pandora’s Box’ Bloomberg UK. <<https://www.bloomberg.com/opinion/articles/2025-06-19/disney-and-comcast-ai-lawsuit-against-midjourney-may-open-a-pandora-s-box?srnd=prognosis&embedded-checkout=true>>.

1.7 Extra LMU AI and T&L-Related Resources

- **General Staff Guidance:**
<https://student.londonmet.ac.uk/your-studies/student-administration/guidance-on-the-use-of-artificial-intelligence/>
- **Centre for Teaching Enhancement, 'AI basics for staff webinar':**
<https://www.londonmet.ac.uk/about/centre-for-teaching-enhancement/cte-events-2023-24/ai-basics-staff-webinar/>
- **Centre for Teaching Enhancement, 'Talking to students about AI':**
https://bblearn.londonmet.ac.uk/ultra/organizations/_53463_1/outline/edit/document/_4124951_1?courseId=_53463_1
- **Centre for Teaching Enhancement, 'Approaches to developing students' AI Literacy':**
https://bblearn.londonmet.ac.uk/ultra/organizations/_53463_1/outline/edit/document/_3989482_1?courseId=_53463_1
- **Centre for Teaching Enhancement, 'Responding to student GenAI use in teaching and learning':**
https://bblearn.londonmet.ac.uk/ultra/organizations/_53463_1/outline/edit/document/_4160976_1?courseId=_53463_1
- **SSSP's Teaching Peer-Review Process (TPRP) guide for improving T&L:**
<https://repository.londonmet.ac.uk/9836/1/TPRP%20Resource%20Pack%20-%20FINAL%20-%202024%20v3.pdf>
- **Library Service's AI Guidance for students:** <https://libguides.londonmet.ac.uk/ai>

2. How to... Use AI as an Assistant When Developing T&L Materials

2.1 Introduction

The overarching message of this section is that educators should largely not use AI tools when they develop learning materials. The temptation for educators to use AI tools is significant. The emergence of these tools offers educators new, highly efficient means to draft lectures, help plan seminar activities, produce assessments and help generate supporting texts such as module handbooks. The appeal here is one of *efficiency*, this technological assistance could free-up educators' valuable time, allowing them to become more research active or contribute to the university's wider academic profile. Rephrased, AI tools are attractive to educators because they promise to empower them to do more with less.

At the same time, the pitfalls of educators over-zealously relying on such tools are significant. Indeed, educators must recognise that if they uncritically rely on these tools, it is likely that they will present low quality teaching materials to learners and negatively impact the reputation of the School. AI-generated T&L materials are known to frequently present false claims as facts, create false references and include biased or discriminatory content.

The reason that AI tools generate such low-quality materials is largely because of their imperfect training data. As discussed in Section 1.4.3, many AI tools reflect colonised, racist and misogynistic ideas because of their training on older academic texts and social media posts. Additionally, the algorithm of AI tools often prioritises a mostly correct, confident response over an unsure, nuanced response or an "I don't know" response. The result is that educators may absorb untrue claims as fact because of the convincing phrasing of the AI tool. Understandably, this could lead an uncritical AI tool user to generate low-quality T&L materials. Certainly, if educators use AI tools, this should be done with great caution; an overreliance on these tools can saliently erode rather than enhance T&L practice.

If educators choose to use an AI tool as an assistant for producing T&L materials, they *must* be transparent with students. It is reasonable for students to expect educators to centrally rely on their own professional insight when they design T&L materials.¹⁸ While AI tools can contribute in a minor capacity, an overreliance on such tools erodes the substantive elements of social science-related higher education (as discussed in Section 1.4). In view of this concern, educators should make clear to students what materials they have created with the assistance of AI. This can be done by marking each document/artifact with the image presented in Appendix 3. If educators feel uneasy about this level of transparency, this should act as a prompt for self-reflection.

¹⁸This is a point exemplified in Hill (n 9).

The following sub-sections provide further guidance for educators to help focus their critical understanding of AI tools when generating T&L materials: to signpost how such technology can help boost educators' productivity while demonstrating how an uncritical acceptance of such tools can, often subtly, undermine their practice and the reputation of the School.

2.2 Consider Doing This...

Consider incorporating these “**dos**” into your T&L practice:

1. Use AI as a **supplementary ideas-partner** and tool to assist in reflection, to expand upon already established lesson plans.
→ **How?** Try using this prompt in your chosen AI tool: “I am planning a lecture on X which focuses on the thinkers of A and B, find me a fun anecdote about each thinker. Also, based on a search of the internet are any of the thinkers' key ideas relevant to any very recent news stories”. The function of AI here is like that of an expanded search engine but, as mentioned, educators must double check any response given by these tools – they are often unreliable and misleading.
2. Use AI to assist in the creation of **low-stakes formative assessments**, such as multiple-choice Mentimeter or Kahoot! quizzes.
→ **How?** Upload your lecture slides to your chosen AI tool and use this prompt: “Generate 20 MCQs and highlight the correct answer”, then review and input select questions into Mentimeter. It is likely that many of the generated questions will reflect a poor understanding of the inputted material. Again, therefore, educators should take a significant amount of time to review the suggestions made by the tool.
3. Ask AI to help you **simplify complex academic jargon** into more accessible language for students.
→ **How?** Input your own expressions into your chosen AI tool and ask it, “rephrase this to make these ideas more accessible to lay persons...”. The response you receive should be used for your reflection. It could also possibly be used as a discussion piece in class, to help you arrive upon more effective ways to communicate complex ideas with students.
4. Remember to **signpost and/or watermark all AI-assisted materials**, be actively transparent with students with your AI tool use.
→ **How?** Educators should include the watermark provided in Appendix 3, this should be applied to all materials made with the assistance of AI. In module handbooks and on Weblearn, educators should also specify to what degree AI tools were used, where appropriate.

2.3 Consider Not Doing This...

Consider these “**do not**s” in view of your own T&L practice:

1. **Do not copy and paste AI-generated content directly** into your teaching materials.
→ **Why?** AI tools can produce factually incorrect information (‘hallucinations’), outdated content and introduce subtle biases. In extreme cases, AI tools can generate racist and misogynistic materials. You are responsible for the quality and accuracy of the materials you provide to students.
2. Do not rely on AI tools to set **learning outcomes** or to make significant choices about what is to be taught.
→ **Why?** There is the risk that educators may overestimate and over rely on the abilities of AI tools, this includes using AI tools to dictate who should be the key thinkers for a lecture or to set key readings. Instead, educators should craft T&L materials by critically reflecting on their knowledge of their field, professional experience and understanding of their students. AI tools are not able to replicate this. Rephrased, AI is indeed a tool, not a teacher.

2.4 Example of Good Practice

Florian teaches the module SQ6090, ‘*Sociological Explanations of Youth Violence*’. As this is the third year of teaching this module, Florian already has a significant amount of teaching materials available. Still, Florian is interested in updating and further refining this material. Before the start of the upcoming term, Florian makes time to engage in verbal, conversational turn-taking with their chosen AI tool. Here, Florian explains the subjects that he is going to teach and why it is important for students to understand this material. With prompting, **the AI tool challenges Florian**. Florian dismisses most of the responses the AI tool generates as they are things he has already considered. In the course of their conversation, the AI tool produced a reference to a publication Florian was unaware of, a book which was released a few months prior on the topic of drill music and urban myths. Florian, no longer using the AI tool, investigates the reference using a traditional search engine. He discovers that while the AI tool produced an inaccurate reference, a very similar book does exist and was released by a reputable academic publisher very recently. Florian is surprised that he was unaware of this text as he follows this area of research closely, he is glad he has now become aware of it. After reading this book, Florian incorporates it into his teaching materials.

Florian returns to the AI tool and begins a new task, he asks the tool to provide **alternative words, phrases and simplified explanations of academic concepts** that are relevant to his module. Here, Florian identifies the AI tool’s explanation of ‘social capital’ as uniquely interesting, the tool conflated Bourdieu's concepts of social capital with that of cultural capital and symbolic violence. Florian finds this conflation to be useful as it can serve as an example of how not to think about Bourdieu's work. For this reason, Florian takes the AI’s account and turns it into a classroom activity where the students should discuss what the tool misunderstood, **encouraging the students to refine their nuanced understanding** of Bourdieu. When converting this AI output into a classroom discussion activity, Florian uses the ‘**AI Assisted Material**’ watermark provided in Appendix 3.

Continuing to update his module, Florian uses an AI tool to generate a short end-of-year quiz. Here, Florian uploads relevant slides of his to the AI tool and asks it to generate a 20-question quiz. The quiz is intended to serve as part of a celebratory, relaxed, activity that will help the module come to a close – **it will not serve as a summative assessment.**

Lastly, Florian **updates the module's Weblearn page and handbook.** Here, Florian takes time to include information regarding how AI tools were used (and not used) in the development of the teaching materials, ensuring high levels of transparency with students.

3. How to... Update Module Assessments (Using the Dual-Model Approach)

3.1 Introduction

SSSP staff should consider making use of the aforementioned dual-model approach (see Section 1.4) when updating their assessments, to help ensure the fair and accurate evaluation of students. AI tools have empowered students with the means to generate large amounts of text with little to no critical thinking or analytical skill. Understandably, this presents a challenge to traditional forms of assessment, particularly the take-home essay and other at-home coursework tasks. Indeed, the use of AI tools to instantly generate full essays and bodies of text with little effort and at no financial cost makes many traditional, unmodified assessments a poor tool to evaluate students' abilities.

In view of this, this guidance recommends that educators update their assessments according to one of two possible models (see the Critical-Learning model in Section 1.4.1 and the Enhanced-Learning model in Section 1.4.2; also see Appendix 1 and 4). In following the Critical-Learning model, educators design-out the possibility that students will rely on AI tools, ensuring that the assessment measures students' unaided ability. Meanwhile, when following the Enhanced-Learning model, educators seek to measure students' ability to leverage technology (AI) to ethically and critically complete a subject-relevant task. By making clear to students which of the two models an assessment fits within, students are better able to understand what it is they are being asked to do and how they will be evaluated. Appendix 1 offers examples of how current assessments can be updated in view of these two models.

As emphasised throughout this document, this guidance recommends that educators overwhelmingly prioritise Critical-Learning over Enhanced-Learning, whether in classroom activities or assessments. Again, this is because Critical-Learning is centrally concerned with developing students' critical thinking skills which are essential for high quality social science-related work; compared with Enhanced-Learning which is at least partly focused on technological proficiency (further discussed in Section 1.4.3). Still, it is permissible for a given module to use both models throughout, switching between them in a dualist fashion for both formative and summative assessments. By following this strategy, educators are able to maintain the academic integrity of the School.

3.2 Consider Doing This...

Here are the “**dos**” for educators when they update module assessments:

1. Following the dual-model approach, **rework current assessments** to be either fully aligned with the Critical-Learning model or the Enhanced-Learning model.
➔ **How?** In Appendix 1 of this guide, there is a table listing some examples of how to adapt traditional assessment to be compliant with both models. Consider reworking your current assessments in view of this. Remember, significant changes to an assessment (such as moving from an essay to an in-class exam) will need approval from the management team / a Principal Lecturer.
2. In your module handbooks and on Weblearn, **clearly state what the dual-model approach is** and how it is used for each of your assessments.
➔ **How?** In Appendix 4 of this guide, there is a brief explainer that can be presented to students. Consider including this in your module’s Weblearn site under the ‘Assessments’ header.
3. When allowing AI use, **require students to sign an AI Transparency Cover Sheet** detailing which tools they used and how they used them. Outside of upholding transparency which is inherently good practice, this promotes metacognition in students.
➔ **How?** In Appendix 2 of this guide, there is an example cover sheet; consider using this in coursework templates for your students. You can also include this as a downloadable link on your module’s Weblearn site.
4. **In class, remind students that assessments are not just evaluative** but they are intended to build their skills.
➔ **How?** For example, explain that the essays they produce will likely not be published and widely read but the skills they develop in critical thinking and effective communication will almost certainly be used in their day-to-day work. For example, by writing, students and researchers think about the act of writing itself; and in doing so, they refine their communication and argumentation skills.

3.3 Consider Not Doing This...

Here are the “**do nots**” for educators when they update module assessments:

1. **Do not assume students understand** what constitutes academic misconduct regarding their use of AI tools.
➔ **Why?** Many of our students, perhaps most, are the first in their family to attend university. This means that there are many things that are entirely new to them regarding what is expected at university, some students report this learning of new expectations as being part of a hidden curriculum.¹⁹ The line between using AI as a helpful tool and using it to cheat (plagiarise) is ambiguous for many of our students.

¹⁹ David Killick, ‘The Role of the Hidden Curriculum: Institutional Messages of Inclusivity’ (2015) 4 Journal of Perspectives in Applied Academic Practice <<https://jpaap.ac.uk/JPAAP/article/view/203>> accessed 5 January 2023.

The result is that they may sincerely believe their use of AI is morally sound and academically acceptable when the same activity is viewed by educators as ethically problematic and a clear violation of academic standards. You must provide explicit and repeated guidance; a lack of clarity is unfair to students. Consider exploring our library's AI guides in your classes as a discussion piece (see Section 1.7), to have students reflect more on their use of AI.

2. **Do not simply add “don't use AI”** to your existing assessments.
 - ➔ **Why?** This is difficult to police and does not address the fundamental issue. As responsible educators, we must design-out the risk of academic misconduct as much as possible. A well-designed Critical-Learning assessment should be resistant to AI by its nature. Meanwhile, modules that incorporate the Enhanced-Learning model should benefit from module leaders clearly explaining to students what uses of AI are acceptable and which are not. Students already have access to the Library Services resources that explain appropriate uses of AI in assessment and staff benefit from the additional resources produced by the Centre for Teaching Enhancement (See the full list in Section 1.7). To further assist educators, see Appendix 5 which lists some general ground rules that can be adapted across a range of Enhanced-Learning assessments.
3. **Do not rely on AI detection software** as your primary tool for upholding academic integrity.
 - ➔ **Why?** First, it is necessary to make clear that students are permitted to use AI tools in Enhanced-Learning assessments. Academic misconduct occurs in such assessments only when standard offences are committed (i.e., plagiarism, falsified references, etc). In these cases, no AI detection software is needed, TurnItIn's standard tools are sufficient to detect this. Otherwise, if a student's piece of work is submitted that is of poor academic quality (as is typical of such tools) then this warrants only a poor mark. Indeed, in such assessments, educators should *accept* and *expect* students to make use of such tools within the limits of standard academic conduct.

Meanwhile, if an educator suspects that a student has made use of an AI tool when completing a Critical-Learning assessment, this would be academic misconduct as such tools are clearly prohibited (and efforts have been made to design-out such a possibility). In this situation, it is important to note that AI detection tools are now known to be unreliable, producing both false positives and false negatives.²⁰ Therefore, an accusation of misconduct should be based on a holistic assessment of the student's work and process, not solely on the output of such unreliable tools. If you have concerns about whether a student used AI, get a second opinion from a colleague and consider asking the student directly. Confrontation of this sort can provoke honesty in students and as mentioned previously, often students do not realise their use of AI is a form of academic misconduct and may therefore be

²⁰ Louie Giray, 'The Problem with False Positives: AI Detection Unfairly Accuses Scholars of AI Plagiarism' (2024) 85 *The Serials Librarian* 181.

sincerely receptive to your guidance. Again, however, owing to the design of the assessment, such an occurrence is highly unlikely.

3.4 Example of Good Practice

Liang is redesigning the final assessment for her module, NU5091 'Critical Perspectives on International Diplomacy'. Previously, the final assessment on her module was a single 3,000-word essay. Recognising the challenges posed by AI, she decides to revise this assessment in view of the **Critical-Learning model**:

Liang approaches and **receives approval from her subject area's Principal Lecturer** to convert her unmodified essay assessment to a 30-minute group debate assessment. At the start of the academic term, Liang explains this change to students, **the assessment is continually discussed as the module progresses**. Three weeks before the assessment date, Liang assigns the students into groups of four. The groups are then divided again, into those who will be either for or against a motion. The students are given a range of debate options to choose from, giving the assessment a degree of flexibility. One of the groups is to discuss the Machiavellian position, "it is better to be feared than loved". Two of the students in this group defend this position whereas the other pair oppose it. The three-week period allows the students to prepare for this assessment. While it is still possible for students to use AI tools at home in their revision of the topic, the focus of the assessment's evaluation is students' oral communication skills and critical engagement with others in the context of the module's taught content. In this way, **the assessment is AI-resistant**.

Meanwhile, Liang is also updating the formative assessment on her other module NU4001 'Introduction to Democratic Governance'. Previously, Liang asked her students to develop a portfolio at home over 10 weeks that discusses how different countries upheld democratic values. Liang was becoming concerned that students were not engaging with this assessment sincerely, and instead relied on AI tools at home to quickly produce materials without engaging meaningfully with the critical thinking component that the assessment was intended to develop. In view of this, Liang redesigned this assessment in view of the **Enhanced-Learning model**:

In this revised formative assessment, students begin by using an AI tool at home to generate a 2,000-word analysis of three countries and their history of upholding democratic values. Following this, Liang reviews these works and identifies a number of false claims. In class, Liang and her students discuss these problems and following this, her students write critical evaluations of their AI's output (three 500-word pieces, focusing on one evaluation for each of their selected countries). In this latter half of the task, the students comment on the errors of the AI tool in how it misrepresents some important historical events and overlooks key nuances that problematically recast the actions of political leaders/organisations. The assessment is focused on evaluating student's ability to conduct academic research which can **discern facts from AI hallucinations**, and demonstrate an ability to identify subtle forms of bias and oversight. Rephrased, **this assessment is intended to develop and evaluate students' AI literacy and critical thinking skills**. In this updated assessment, the **students are required to submit a declaration of their use of AI tools** (see Appendix 2). This change in assessment did not require that Liang's module be revalidated by an external body because of the formative nature of the assessment and because it was still a form of coursework.

4. How to... Use AI for Administrative Tasks

4.1 Introduction

AI tools can help educators to do more with less by streamlining administrative tasks; at the same time, educators should be aware that the misapplication of such tools can erode their professionalism and the School's reputation. An over-reliance on AI tools can be inappropriate, it can lead to communication that feels impersonal and in extreme cases, it can be used to shirk responsibility. Indeed, consider how AI tools can, but should not, be used to mark students' work, write reference letters or provide students with careers advice. In these cases, AI could generate a plausible response but this would be superficial and lack true professional insight. Above all, it is categorically unethical. The role of educators is a demanding and highly skilled one, it requires excellent pastoral skills, high levels of empathy and understanding and an ability to approach sensitive issues respectfully whilst fostering the values of free speech and intellectual inquiry. AI tools cannot replace this function of educators. This section clarifies the boundaries of appropriate AI tool usage for educators, enabling them to better capture the efficiency benefits of such tools and to maintain their high professional standards.

4.2 Consider Doing This...

Here are the “**dos**” for educators when they use AI for administrative and correspondence-related tasks:

1. Ask an AI tool **to review the tone of an email** you have drafted.
➔ **How?** In your preferred AI tool, try using this prompt before including your draft email: “Can you make this more supportive, formal and concise?”. It will almost certainly produce something that you cannot use in its entirety; however, there may be word choices or a rephrasing that you could adopt. Again, the key here is to be critical and selective. Importantly, ensure that the email draft is generic and free of any confidential information (names, places, etc).
2. Utilise AI as a **grammar and spell-checking tool**.
➔ **How?** In your preferred AI tool, try using this prompt before including your draft text: “Check this for grammar and spelling issues, and highlight sections that make use of passive voice and verbs. List your recommended changes”. As is typical with AI tools, it is likely that the draft it produces is not of a high quality, it may include redundant words or even include passive verbs despite your direction not to. The value here is that it may spot some important errors or provide some valuable suggestions for improvement. Indeed, while the tool may offer five suggestions only one may be useful.

3. Use AI tools to generate **quick drafts for minor bureaucratic tasks**.
 - ➔ Such tasks include completing a short bio of yourself for LinkedIn or use it to generate a summary of your publications which could be used in an end-of-year review. In these instances, small factual errors are not critical and there is little emotional harm that can be committed. Rephrased, the efficiency benefits outweigh the potential negatives. Still, educators should be critical here and engage in error-checking; it is typical for all AI-generated material to contain at least some inaccuracies.

4.3 Consider Not Doing This...

Here are the “**do nots**” for educators when they use AI for administrative and correspondence-related tasks:

1. Do not use **AI to write emails**, especially regarding **sensitive or pastoral matters**.
 - ➔ **Why?** Students requiring pastoral support need genuine human empathy and understanding. An automated or even semi-automated response can come across as dismissive and uncaring, potentially damaging your relationship with the student.
2. Do not input **students’ personal information** or the content of **confidential emails** into a public AI tool.
 - ➔ **Why?** This is a serious breach of privacy and data protection (including GDPR). Some AI tools use uploaded files and text for training data, meaning others who publicly use the technology could indirectly gain access to the data you upload. Indeed, by uploading personal information and confidential emails, educators can inadvertently violate the trust students place in them and breach university policy. (Educators should also note that many AI tools have an option where users can ‘opt-out’ from participating in sharing their uploads/prompts as training data. It is recommended that all staff opt out as default as a safeguarding measure).
3. Do not use AI-generated text to provide **academic feedback (or mark assessments)**.
 - ➔ **Why?** Providing feedback is a key pedagogical skill. Students benefit from your specific, expert insight. Generic AI feedback is unlikely to be helpful and undermines the integrity of the assessment process. This also extends to providing references and general employment advice, such tasks are key to the pedagogical role. Using AI in this way erodes educators’ practice and relatedly, the School’s reputation.

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Glossary

Agentic AI

A type of AI that can autonomously perform complex, multi-step tasks to achieve a user's goal by interacting with multiple applications. For example, it could be prompted to research a topic, summarise the findings, and email a draft to a specified contact.

AI Detection Software

Tools designed to analyse a piece of text to determine the likelihood that it was generated by an AI model. This guidance document cautions that these tools are often unreliable and can produce both false positives and false negatives.

AI Literacy

Technological competency involving AI tools, focusing on the ability to critically evaluate and ethically use such tools. This document views this as an increasingly important employability skill.

AI Tools

A general term used throughout the guidance to refer to the broad category of software and platforms that utilise artificial intelligence including generative, agentic, and other forms of AI.

Algorithm

A set of rules, instructions, and statistical models that an AI system follows to process data, learn from it, and generate an output.

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is an EU law that governs UK institutions' collection, processing, and storage of personal information. The guidance warns against inputting any sensitive or personal student data into public AI tools.

Formative Assessment

Low-stakes assessment activities designed to monitor student learning and provide ongoing feedback. The guidance suggests using AI to help create formative assessments like multiple-choice quizzes.

General AI (Artificial General Intelligence, also referred to as 'AGI')

A theoretical form of AI that can learn and apply its knowledge across a wide range of tasks at a level equivalent to or exceeding that of a human. This technology does not yet exist.

Generative AI

A category of AI that can synthesise already existing text, images, audio and code to create new media. For example, OpenAI's ChatGPT can generate a novel image of a cat by algorithmically synthesising three pre-existing images of cats.

Hallucination

An instance where an AI model produces information that is false, fabricated, or nonsensical but presents it as factual and confident.

Hidden Curriculum

The hidden curriculum refers to the unwritten, unofficial, and often unintended lessons, values, and norms that students learn in school through social interactions and the overall educational environment.

Large Language Model (LLM)

The foundational technology behind many generative AI tools. LLMs are trained on massive amounts of data, enabling them to generate human-like language.

Metacognition

The process of thinking about one's thinking. In the HE context, educators can require their students to document how they used an AI tool to complete a task; and in doing so, guide students to reflect on their learning and research process.

Near-General AI

A term for highly advanced AI tools or systems that demonstrate capabilities across a broad spectrum of tasks, approaching but not yet reaching the level of General AI.

Pastoral Support

The provision of support for a student's personal and emotional well-being. The guidance strongly advises against using AI for communications related to pastoral care, as these situations require genuine human empathy.

Pedagogy

The method and practice of teaching and learning.

Prompt

An initial instruction, question, or text input provided by a user of an AI tool, given to direct its output.

The Dual-Model Approach

An overarching strategy for navigating the issues that AI tools cause on the HE T&L process. In this system, educators should overwhelmingly make use of the Critical-Learning model throughout their practice by prioritising traditional pedagogical methods that design-out the possibility of AI tool interference. Meanwhile, supplementary to this, educators can make use of the Enhanced-Learning model. This latter model allows educators to integrate AI tools into their T&L practice but clear limits and expectations are set of staff and students. By having access to both, educators have the freedom to make the most of AI tools while also protecting against the negative impact of such tools.

Viva (or Viva Voce)

An oral examination in which a student answers questions to defend their academic work.

Appendix 1 – Updating Assessments Following the Dual-Model Approach

Current Unmodified Assessment	Update using the Critical-Learning Model	Update using the Enhanced-Learning Model
<p>Essay or other at-home written report / coursework</p>	<p><i>Option 1:</i> Convert this to a handwritten essay under exam/timed conditions. (Students could also make use of computers granted there is appropriate exam hall invigilation). The exam question can be either seen or unseen.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>OR</i></p> <p><i>Option 2:</i> Convert to a multiple-choice question exam under timed conditions.</p>	<p><i>Option 3:</i> Continue with the essays/report assessment as usual, allowing students to prepare their submissions at home.</p> <p>Importantly, educators must make clear to students that AI tools can be used in this assessment but that academic misconduct rules still apply. Educators will need to guide students here regarding what constitutes appropriate AI tool use (see Appendix 5 for further guidance; also see the library resources listed in Section 1.7 which are aimed at students).</p> <p>Students should also make use of the cover sheet in Appendix 2.</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>OR</i></p> <p><i>Option 4:</i> Set students the task of critically analysing a document that you (the educator) have generated using an AI tool. The document you present to students could be a case study, policy or historic event. The task here is for students to investigate what is incorrect or analytically</p>

		<p>‘thin’ about the material you present to them. (Remember, when producing AI materials, include the watermark provided in Appendix 3).</p> <p>Importantly, educators must make clear to students that AI tools can be used in this assessment but that academic misconduct rules still apply. Educators will need to guide students here regarding what constitutes appropriate AI tool use (see Appendix 5 for further guidance; also see the library resources listed in Section 1.7 which are aimed at students).</p> <p>Students should also make use of the cover sheet in Appendix 2.</p> <p><i>OR</i></p> <p><i>Option 5:</i> Similarly to Option 4, and as a novel approach to essay writing, ask students to submit an AI-generated draft alongside their final version, explaining edits and improvements.</p> <p>Importantly, educators must make clear to students that AI tools can be used in this assessment but that academic misconduct rules still apply. Educators will need to guide students here regarding what constitutes appropriate AI tool use (see Appendix 5 for further guidance; also see the library resources listed in Section 1.7 which are aimed at students).</p>
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		<p>Students should also make use of the cover sheet in Appendix 2.</p>
<p>Slide presentation</p>	<p><i>Option 1:</i> Convert into a mini viva voce / oral exam without any slide presentation aspect.</p> <p>OR</p> <p><i>Option 2:</i> Convert into a group debate project (as exemplified in Section 3.4), there is no slide presentation component here.</p>	<p><i>Option 3:</i> Continue as normal with a live, in-class presentation. Students are to produce their slides at home and they are expected to use AI tools. Students are centrally evaluated on the Q&A aspect of their presentation. Indeed, the focus of the evaluation should be on students' ability to fully articulate an understanding of the module's subject matter and offer critical insights when asked.</p> <p>Importantly, educators must make clear to students that AI tools can be used in this assessment but that academic misconduct rules still apply. Educators will need to guide students here regarding what constitutes appropriate AI tool use (see Appendix 5 for further guidance; also see the library resources listed in Section 1.7 which are aimed at students).</p> <p>Where appropriate, students should make use of the 'AI Assisted Material' watermark provided in Appendix 3.</p> <p>Students should also make use of the cover sheet in Appendix 2 when submitting to Weblearn / TurnItIn.</p> <p>OR</p> <p><i>Option 4:</i> Convert into a peer-teaching exercise. Here, students are tasked</p>

		<p>with teaching the class/their peers a concept. While students are able to prepare teaching materials at home, the focus of evaluation is on how effectively they can communicate complex, subject-relevant ideas to others.</p> <p>Importantly, educators must make clear to students that AI tools can be used in this assessment but that academic misconduct rules still apply. Educators will need to guide students here regarding what constitutes appropriate AI tool use (see Appendix 5 for further guidance; also see the library resources listed in Section 1.7 which are aimed at students).</p> <p>Where appropriate, students should make use of the 'AI Assisted Material' watermark provided in Appendix 3.</p> <p>Students should also make use of the cover sheet in Appendix 2 when submitting to Weblearn / TurnItIn.</p>
<p>Dissertation project</p>	<p><i>Option 2:</i> In addition to Option 1, educators could add an oral/viva voce assessment to their dissertation modules. This oral component would not be able to serve as a total replacement for the traditional take-home dissertation project. However, elements of the Critical-Learning model can still be embedded using this method.</p>	<p><i>Option 1:</i> Similar to essays, dissertation projects can remain as at-home tasks.</p> <p>Importantly, educators must make clear to students that AI tools can be used in this assessment but that academic misconduct rules still apply. Educators will need to guide students here regarding what constitutes appropriate AI tool use (see Appendix 5 for further guidance; also see the library</p>

		<p>resources listed in Section 1.7 which are aimed at students).</p> <p>Students should also make use of the cover sheet in Appendix 2.</p>
<p>Please note, the above options are presented as suggestions only. There are other assessment methods that are compatible with the dual-model approach. Educators should consider these amongst others when updating their T&L practice:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendance as a basis for assessment (i.e., consistent weekly attendance and contribution to class activities contributes to the student’s module grade). • Case simulations (including role-play). • Practical / laboratory or fieldwork reports. • Peer-review exercises. • In class portfolio/course-work tasks. 		

Appendix 2 – AI Transparency Cover Sheet

This statement aims to inform the reader of the author's/researcher's use of AI tools in the creation of this attached document. The below statement serves to promote transparency regarding the author's/researcher's AI tool use. What follows are some reflections from the author/researcher.

Guidance for Authors/Researchers

- **Transparency is a celebrated part of research**; much like the use of referencing, researchers should make clear how they have used AI tools to demonstrate how they arrived upon their ideas.
- This statement **must be completed and submitted** when you have used AI tools to assist in the completion of an AI-inclusive (Enhanced-Learning) assessment.
- Failure to provide this statement when AI has been used may constitute **academic misconduct**.
- The statement should be **honest, specific and written in your own words** (not AI-generated).

AI Tools Used, Purpose & Extent of Use

Please list all AI tools (e.g., ChatGPT, Grammarly, Bing AI, Claude, etc.) used during the preparation of your work and explain what you used these tools for.

Example: I used ChatGPT to brainstorm initial ideas for the introduction and Grammarly for grammar and spelling corrections. All analysis and arguments were written by myself.

Critical Reflections on Usefulness/Limitations of the Used AI Tools

Reflect on the usefulness and limitations of the AI tools you used.

Example: Copilot helped me generate ideas quickly, but some statements that the tool generated were inaccurate.

By attaching this form to your assignment and submitting it for marking, you confirm that:

‘This statement accurately reflects how I used AI tools in the preparation of this work.’

Submission of this form constitutes your digital signature, dated at the time of submission.

Appendix 3 – AI Assisted Material Logo

Appendix 4 – Dual-Model T&L Brief

What follows is a brief outline that can be included on Weblearn and in module handbooks to help students understand the dual-model approach.

The Dual-Model Approach to Teaching & Learning

This module makes use of a dual-Model approach to teaching and learning (T&L). Most of your learning on this module will follow the Critical-Learning model, which emphasises the development of your critical thinking skills free of any support from artificial intelligence (AI) tools. On rarer occasions, your module leader may guide your learning using the Enhanced-Learning model which does allow you to use AI tools in ways relevant to your subject area. These two models can be used to set the ground rules of classroom activities and importantly, to let you know how to complete your assessments. Some assessments do not allow students to use AI tools (these assessments reflect the Critical-Learning model). Other assessments allow you to use AI tools (these reflect the Enhanced-Learning model). For each assessment you undertake, make sure to speak to your module leader to ensure that you fully understand what is expected of you.

To better understand the dual-model approach, it can be helpful to use the analogy of a ship with two sails. As you begin the module, your module leader acts like a captain who leads their passengers (students) on a set educational route. The mainsail that is absolutely required for the ship to make its journey is the Critical-Learning model. As an option, the captain (or module leader) could use a secondary, smaller sail (the Enhanced-Learning model) but this is not required to make the journey. In this way, most of your experience on the module will be AI-free; only at select times and for select activities will your module leader allow AI, if at all. The default AI tool used by LMU is Microsoft's Copilot which all staff and students have enterprise access to.

Critical-Learning Model = The Mainsail

- Prioritises the development of students' **independent critical thinking, reflection, non-digital communication** and **problem-solving skills**.
- Educators **design-out** the possibility of students relying on AI in the T&L process, ensuring that traditional pedagogical practices retain their value.

Enhanced-Learning Model = Optional

- By contrast, this model incorporates AI into the teaching and learning process as to build students' **subject-relevant technological proficiency** and **AI literacy**.
- It allows students to use AI tools in certain activities and assessments.
- Here, AI is treated as a **complement to critical thinking, not a replacement**.

Appendix 5 – Appropriate AI Tool Use for Enhanced-Learning Assessments

Appropriate Uses of AI Tools

In addition to the guidance presented to you by the Library Services team regarding AI use for assessments, consider the following. These points illustrate some broad appropriate uses of AI when you engage in an Enhanced-Learning assessment. Remember, most assessments on your degree do not allow any AI use at all by students, so make sure that you have permission to use AI tools before following the below guidance.

[1] You may use AI tools for inspiration or to overcome writer's block.

Like checking Wikipedia or watching a fun infographic video on a subject you would otherwise find difficult to understand, AI tools can be used to help build momentum for engaging with more challenging but powerful academic texts. In this way, AI tools can be useful in the very early, experimental part of the research process. You should, however, quickly move on to directly reading academic texts – that is where the real learning takes place!

[2] You may use AI tools when proofreading, to check for spelling and grammar issues.

AI tools can help you complete a line-by-line spelling and grammar review of your written work. Confusingly, AI tools can highlight well-written sections of text as containing errors - this is a quirk of AI tools. Despite this, these tools can spot genuine errors that you may have missed. For this reason, even though these tools are not perfect, they can be a useful part of the proofreading process.

[3] You may use AI tools to help you think about your thinking.

Thinking about thinking is a key part of the learning process, it makes us more effective communicators. Thinking about how we present arguments and what makes a particular point powerful is a key part of crafting effective essays, reports and other forms of communication. By using AI tools as a type of thought partner, you are able to explore different ways of expressing an idea and in doing so, you can gain perspective on how you express your arguments and ideas. The important part here is to reflect on your own expressions in view of the taught material; this is in contrast to uncritically accepting any rephrasing or counter-argument presented by an AI tool.

Remember to use the 'AI Transparency Cover Sheet' for all Enhanced-Learning Assessments!

Inappropriate Uses of AI Tools

In an academic context, there are many inappropriate uses of AI, even when an assessment is openly AI-inclusive (following the Enhanced-Learning model). You should generally refrain from using AI tools unless expressly for the above 'appropriate' reasons or for those that your module leader specifies. What follows are only some of the common unacceptable uses of AI which you should avoid, these are presented as 'Do not' statements.

[1] Do not submit AI text as your own (copy-and-paste)

There are many reasons not to do this. A key reason is that the information provided by AI tools is often untrue or misleading. Another important reason is that AI tools rely on other people's work to generate answers; as a result, these tools can produce text that includes significant chunks of other people's unmodified work. By using such work and presenting it as your own, you are committing plagiarism, a form of academic misconduct. For this reason, copying and pasting directly from AI tools is not an acceptable practice in academia.

[2] Do not trust the references or arguments generated by an AI tool.

Again, AI tools often present inaccurate information confidently to users. The result is that users can find an AI response believable but upon closer inspection, it becomes clear that the requested references or arguments are entirely made-up.

[3] Do not ask an AI tool to fully restructure or reorganise your work and submit this as your own work.

AI tools have a particular style of writing which is typically considered poor in academic contexts. More specifically, these tools are often unoriginal, flowery and uncritical. The result is that when students ask such tools to restructure or reorganise their text, the tool can erode the quality of their work – even when specifically prompted not to do so!

Appendix 6 – FAQs

Q1: How Can I Identify Student Work That Has Been Generated by AI?

You cannot definitively know if a student used AI when producing a submitted piece of work, unless they directly admit this is the case. AI detection software is unreliable and modern AI tools can modify their phrasing specifically to deceive markers by adding spelling errors and the like. Instead of focusing on detection and the punishment of students, this guidance document recommends that educators either design-out the likelihood a student will use an AI tool to complete an assessment (following the Critical-Learning model) or redesign their assessments in such a way that AI tool-use is explicitly encouraged (following the Enhanced-Learning model).

Q2: What Is the University’s Stance on Using AI Detection Tools?

As stated throughout this guidance document, AI detection tools are unreliable; they often produce both false positives and false negatives. Therefore, such detection tools should not be used.

Q3: How Can We Ensure Fairness for Students Who Are Not Using AI?

Fairness can be ensured by redesigning assessments using the dual-model approach (see Section 1.4). This involves educators making a binary choice regarding the redesign of their assessments: either make assessments follow the Critical-Learning model and make them AI-resistant or make assessments in view of the Enhanced-Learning model by making them exclusively AI-inclusive. By clearly communicating which model an assessment follows, all students understand the expectations of the assessment and how they are being evaluated.

Q4: How Can I Design Assessments That Are Resistant to AI?

Revisit Section 3 and Appendix 1. This guidance document offers educators examples of how traditional assessments such as at-home essays can be modernised to become AI-resistant.

